

Lubricant and Lubricant Additive Degradation: Implications for Cabin Air Quality

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ABSTRACT

The composition and decomposition chemistry of the lubricants used in commercial aircraft was described. The common reactions of ester base stocks include hydrolysis and oxidation which results in the formation of aldehydes, anhydrides and a new set of organic acids. This explains why there is an increase in the number of compounds in the lubricant upon use. The chemistry of phosphate ester additives was also described along with the reasons for their continued use. High temperatures can result in isomerization of the cresol along with hydrolysis and addition reactions leading to a wide range of phosphate ester products. The implications of lubricant degradation on cabin air quality is also considered.

INTRODUCTION

Lubricants serve a number of purposes, including the reduction of friction, the reduction of wear and the removal of heat from bearings. The oil is normally held in place by various types of seals, but even the best designed seals will leak a small amount of the lubricant. Cabin air for most commercial airliners is drawn from the compressor stage of the engine and fed directly into the aircraft cabin. This air normally contains small amounts of the leaked lubricant and its decomposition products, and in the case of seal failure, much larger amounts of decomposed lubricant. The composition of the used

lubricant and the pathways for its degradation will be investigated in the paper.

Lubricant specifications

Lubricants used in commercial airliners all are required to meet specification AS5780C,¹ which specifies the properties of the lubricant, but not the composition. The performance specification means that while all oils have similar properties and are generally compatible, the composition of the different oils can vary. The performance specification limits the oils to synthetic esters, which require both antioxidants to improve the stability of the oil and phosphate esters to improve the lubricating properties and reduce engine wear. The specifications also limit the reactivity of the oil, but most testing is done at the bulk oil temperature limit and not the higher temperatures experienced within the engine.

Lubricant composition

Modern aerospace lubricants are made from a synthetic ester base stock. The esters are based on a highly hindered alcohol that reacts with various carboxylic acids to form esters as is seen in Figure 1. The use of various carboxylic acids enable fine tuning of properties such as pour point, flash point, viscosity and viscosity index. The use of mixtures of acids and alcohols is preferred because it provides for a wider liquid temperature range and allows for a better combination of physical and chemical properties. A typical lubricant, analyzed by gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC-MS), is shown in Figure 2.

While ester-based lubricants have excellent physical and chemical properties, additives are used to reduce oxidation and reduce bearing wear.

Lubricant additives

Lubricants, in order to meet the specifications typically require a number of additives to reduce the reactivity of the oil and modify other properties. The additives typically include antioxidants, metal ion deactivators and anti-wear of extreme pressure additives.

Figure 1— Polyols and carboxylic acids used in the preparation of lubricant esters

Figure 2 — The gas chromatography-mass spectrometry total ion chromatogram for a lubricant showing the multiple components

$$P = \left(\left(\frac{\gamma - \varepsilon \sin \gamma}{(1 - \varepsilon^2)^{3/2}} \right) - \left(\frac{\gamma - 2\varepsilon \sin \gamma + \varepsilon^2 \gamma / 2 + (\varepsilon^2 \sin 2\gamma) / 4}{(1 - \varepsilon \cos \gamma)^{3/2} (1 - \varepsilon^2)^{3/2}} \right) \right) (6U\eta R/c)$$

Figure 3 – Pressure and temperature conditions predicted using the Reynolds equation

Antioxidants

Antioxidants are added as a way to reduce oxidation reactions of the base stock. They typically act by reacting with free radicals such as the hydroperoxy radical that is formed by reaction of organic compounds with oxygen. For aerospace applications, amine antioxidants are typically used. Among the most common are N-phenyl-1-naphthylamine (PANA) and 4,4'-diocetylphenyl amine (DODPA).

Anti-wear/Extreme Pressure

Anti-wear and extreme pressure additives reduce friction and wear by forming a hard and slippery surface on the bearing. Typically, phosphorus and sulfur compounds form the appropriate coating. The use of sulfur compounds would be unacceptable due to the odor associated with them and the use of bleed air for cabin pressurization. That leaves the only effective option as the phosphate esters.

Metal deactivators

Metal atom deactivators are compounds that react to stabilize metal ions that end up dissolved in the lubricant.

These are typically benzotriazole or chelating Schiff bases.

Degradation conditions

Lubricants in turbine engines are exposed to a wide range of conditions, from very low external temperatures, to bulk oil temperatures recorded for the oil, to even hotter engine parts and the extreme conditions of temperature and pressure in the contact regions within bearings. The range of temperature that the lubricant might experience for long periods of time are established in the specifications as the pour point and flash point temperature. In addition, oxidative corrosion testing is conducted at the highest bulk oil temperature for the oil. Lubricants are likely to experience substantially higher temperatures for short periods within the engine. Engine temperatures are typically about 500°C. Contact with engine parts as high as 1700°C are also possible within the engine.²

A more difficult question to answer is the stress on the lubricant that is generated within the contact regions of the bearing. The Reynolds equation allows estimates of these temperature and pressure conditions. The

Figure 4 – Thermal oxidative decomposition of lubricant base stocks

Reynolds equation and the pressures and temperatures predicted are shown in Figure 3.³

Lubricant base stock degradation

Ester based lubricant base stocks have several low and moderate temperature degradation routes. Probably the simplest route would be through hydrolysis. This route is possible due to the roughly 500 ppm solubility of water in the base stock. Further evidence of this route is the presence of acids and partial esters from the base stock in the GC-MS of most oil samples.

A second common reaction of the base stock is the oxidation of the base stock with molecular oxygen. This reaction which is thought to proceed through a radical mechanism involving the abstraction of a hydrogen atom to form the hydroperoxy radical, yields acids, aldehydes, ketones and anhydrides as is shown in Figure 4.

At higher temperatures a wide range of reactions can occur. The pyrolysis of a lubricant at 350°C yields a complex mixture that shows at least 634 distinct peaks, of which 170 were identified.⁴ Among the compounds that were identified include acids, aldehydes, ketones, phosphate esters and polycyclic aromatic compounds. It is likely that the latter two groups are a result of the additives and not the base stock. At higher temperature more complex mixtures with a wider range of compounds might be expected to be formed. It was also observed in a separate study that carbon monoxide is formed at levels up to 150 ppm.⁵

Phosphate ester degradation

Throughout this conference there has been a discussion of the health problems phosphate esters cause, raising the question, why are they still in use. Phosphate esters, primarily triaryl phosphates are added to improve the

Figure 5 — Reactions of triaryl phosphate at the surface of a metal

Figure 6 — Formation of a solid lubricious film from the iron surface and phosphate ester

Figure 7 — Transesterification of a base stock polyol ester with a phosphate ester

extreme pressure performance of the polyol ester basestock. The phosphate esters bind to bearing surfaces forming a film that lubricates the bearing during startup and also under conditions of extreme stress, reducing the possibility of catastrophic failure.

Phosphate esters are known to chemically bond to the surface of bearings forming a lubricious film. The initial reaction of the phosphate can proceed in two ways depending on the degree of oxidation of the surface at that point as is shown in Figure 5. In the case of an oxidized surface, cresol is released and the phosphate is bound to the surface. If there is limited oxygen present the aromatic ring is transferred to another molecule and a bound phosphate is again the result.⁶

After the initial reaction of the phosphate with the metal surface, the reaction can continue releasing the alcohols leaving a polyphosphate at the surface of the bearing. Under conditions of wear, the coating wears away, but is reformed by reaction with the lubricant additive, leaving the bearing protected. The surface film is shown in Figure 6.

Phosphate esters react in a number of ways at temperatures of 400-500°C. One of the reactions allows for the isomerization of various groups on the aromatic ring. This reaction can be a particular problem due to the known neurotoxicity of *ortho* Tricresyl phosphate (TCP) isomers. Even though modern TCP is free of the *ortho* isomers, isomerization causes the formation of small amounts of the *ortho* isomer under conditions found in turbine engines.

Other reactions that have been observed at temperature near the operating temperature of the engine are transesterification reactions between the lubricant and the phosphate ester. In transesterification, the alcohols and acids of two esters change partners as is shown in Figure 7. Transesterification can result in a whole new class of potentially toxic compounds within the oil.

CONCLUSIONS

The chemistry of the lubricant base stock generates a wide range of compounds that are expected to be present in cabin air at low levels under normal

circumstances. While the toxicology of some compounds is known on an individual basis, the inhalation toxicity of highly complex mixture, including the aerosols associated with smoke is not understood. Given all of these uncertainties, the use of unfiltered bleed air for pressurization presents an unacceptable risk to both passengers and crew.

References

1. MIL-PRF-23699G, *Performance Specification: Lubricating Oil, Aircraft Turbine Engine, Synthetic Base, NATO Code Numbers: O-152, O-154, O-156, and O-167 (13-MAR-2014) 23699 Specs. 2014. Available from: <http://everyspec.com/MIL-PRF/MIL-PRF-010000-29999/MIL-P.>; 2014.*
2. Johnson DW. Lubricants for Turbine Engines. In: *Recent Progress in Some Aircraft Technologies*. INTECH; 2016:35-53. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/62394>
3. Hills, J E. Decomposition of Polyol Ester Lubricants Containing Tricresyl Phosphate in the Presence of Metal Carbides: ". M.S. Thesis. 2009.
4. EASA. *Research Project: AVOIL. Characterisation of the Toxicity of Aviation Turbine Engine Oils after Pyrolysis. Final Report EASA_REP_RESEA_2015_2*. Cologne: European Aviation Safety Agency; 2017. <https://www.easa.europa.eu/the-agency/procurement/calls-for-tender/easa2015hvp23>.
5. Van Netten C, Leung V. Hydraulic fluids and jet engine oil: Pyrolysis and aircraft air quality. *Arch Environ Health*. 2001;56(2):181-186. doi:10.1080/00039890109604071
6. Johnson D, Hils J, Johnson DW, Hils JE. Phosphate Esters, Thiophosphate Esters and Metal Thiophosphates as Lubricant Additives. *Lubricants*. 2013;1(4):132-148. doi:10.3390/lubricants1040132